

FACTORS AFFECTING THE FORMATION OF INTESTINAL MICROFLORA AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN INFANTS BORN OF MOTHERS PROPRIETARY TO ALLERGIC REACTIONS

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Abstract

The human microbiota is an ecological system that has developed as a result of the evolution of various microorganisms that inhabit the open spaces of the body and provide the biochemical, metabolic and immunological balance necessary to protect health [1]. The largest population of microbes is found in the gastrointestinal tract, especially the large intestine. Thus, about 10¹⁴ bacterial cells live in the human large intestine, which is ten times more than the total number of cells in the body [2]. The microbiota of each person has a unique composition and develops throughout life [4]. Intestinal microflora is of great importance for human health, ensuring the continuity of colonization of the mucous membranes of the digestive system, regulating important metabolic and physiological functions, stimulating the development of the immune system and maintaining the homeostasis of the body. From this point of view, the process of formation of the intestinal microbiota is of great interest. In this article we present the results of our research in the direction of identifying factors influencing the formation of intestinal microflora in newborns and the development of atopic dermatitis in these babies born from mothers prone to allergic reactions.

Keywords: newborn baby, microbiota, intestinal microflora, atopy, atopic dermatitis.

Introduction. The formation of intestinal microflora in newborns can be influenced by many factors. Thus, the intestinal flora of children born vaginally (naturally) is usually represented by microorganisms of the genera *Prevotella*, *Sneathia* and *Lactobacillus*, which make up the vaginal microflora of the mother. Infants born by cesarean section have a lower diversity of bacterial species, including fewer bifidobacteria and Bacteroides, in their gut microbiota compared to infants born vaginally [38, 44]. As is known, the formation of intestinal microflora in children is significantly influenced by many factors, including the method of delivery (natural or surgical), the method of feeding the child, environmental factors, diseases of the mother and some medications taken during pregnancy, as well as atopic conditions of the mother [49, 50]. Atopy means an abnormal immune response of the body to certain substances, in other words, an excessive tendency of a person to allergic reactions. Although atopy itself is not considered a disease, people who are prone to allergic reactions are more likely to develop conditions such as atopic dermatitis, asthma and allergic rhinitis. Atopic dermatitis, considered one of the early and frequent signs of changes in the constitution and reactivity of the newborn's body, occupies one of the most important places among modern pediatric problems. As mentioned above, the dynamics of the formation of intestinal microflora depends on many factors, and its disruption increases the risk of developing atopy in a newborn child [1]. In atopy, even before the development of allergies in a child, the composition of the intestinal microbiota has a number of unique features [2]. Thus, any change in the microenvironment that contributes to the development of sensitization in a newborn child can

play an important role in the development of allergic reactions, which can form due to the activation of opportunistic microorganisms in the intestine [3, 4, 5].

Goal of the work. Study of factors influencing the formation of intestinal microflora and the development of atopic conditions in newborns.

Material and methods. 34 newborns (20 boys, 14 girls) born to mothers prone to allergic reactions were examined. The diagnosis of atopic dermatitis was made on the basis of anamnestic data and the clinical picture of the disease, as well as the results of microbiological examination of stool.

Result. The study found that 26 (76.5%) mothers suffered from food allergies, 5 (14.7%) mothers suffered from urticaria, 3 (8.8%) mothers suffered from angioedema. The main cause of allergies in them is predominantly food products (honey, sweets, chocolate and eggs), 14 (41.2%) mothers took penicillin drugs during pregnancy due to exacerbation of chronic diseases, 6 (17.6%) mothers had bacterial vaginosis. It was found that 5 (14.7%) mothers gave birth surgically (cesarean section), 29 (85.3%) mothers had a physiological birth. 27 (79.4%) children with normal body weight (3275±220 g) and height (51.2±0.7 cm) were born full-term, and 7 (20.6%) children with signs of perinatal CNS damage were born premature. In 12 (35.3%) newborns, a connection was determined with the development of atopy, manifested by miliaria and strophulus in 24 (70.6%) children, gnathostoma of the scalp in 26 children. (76.5%) children, 21 (61.8%) children had boils of the I-II degree, 16 (47.1%) children had various elements of the rash, 11 (32.4%) children had vesiculopustulosis and wet eczema with a family history. It was found that the listed allergy symptoms more often occur in 22

(64.7%) children who were on mixed and artificial feeding (the remaining 12 (35.3%) children were on natural feeding). In addition to atopic dermatitis, 10 (29.4%) patients had signs of acute bronchial obstruction and perinatal central nervous system damage, and 7 (20.6%) children had episodes of increased hyperexcitability. The main complaint of mothers was unexplained crying and sudden restlessness in 20 (58.8%) children, paroxysmal intestinal colic during feeding in 9 (26.5%) children. On the other hand, it was found that 8 (23.5%) mothers received antibacterial and 3 (8.8%) hormonal drugs due to suspected intrauterine infections. Microbiological examination of stool in all children revealed significant quantitative and qualitative changes in the intestinal microbiota, which was manifested by both a low frequency of detection of intestinal microflora and its significant rarity in quantitative terms. Thus, *bifidobacteria* were detected only in 25 (73.5%), fermentative *full-fledged Escherichia* - in 20 (58.8%), *non-hemolytic enterococci* - in 13 (38.2%) patients.

Conclusion. Thus, it has been established that among the risk factors that can affect the formation of intestinal microbiota and the development of atopic dermatitis in newborns from mothers prone to allergic reactions, atopic conditions of the mother, intrauterine infections, early transfer of the child to mixed and artificial feeding, as well as drugs, taken by the mother during pregnancy and childbirth, occupy an important place. At the same time, even minor changes in intestinal biosenosis and disturbances in microbial colonization can play an important role in the genesis of sensitization in a newborn child and the development of the allergic component.

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